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THE USE OF VIDEO FILMS IN THE PROCESS OF LEARNING ENGLISH

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Abstract: *This article examines the most effective method of teaching foreign languages. Working with videos introduces students to the accepted norms of speech interaction and the peculiarities of the communicative behavior of native speakers of the studied language. Movies broaden the horizons, students can learn a lot about the country of the language being studied, about its culture and inhabitants, which facilitates communication with native speakers, makes it effective and successful.*

Key words: *English learning language, audio-visual aids, authentic materials, motivation in learning, language acquisition*

One of the main tasks of teaching foreign language speech in a modern school is the development of communicative skills. But mastering this type of activity is fraught with great difficulties, in particular with a limited opportunity to communicate with native speakers and use conversational skills outside of school. Modern technologies allow us to expand the scope of the lesson and lead to the need to use new forms of learning. One of these forms is a video lesson [1, p. 31], on which authentic animated, artistic, documentary and popular science films can be used. They are considered the most effective and promising means of teaching a foreign language, due to the great informativeness of the visual-auditory series, as well as the dynamism of the image. The use of video support in the lesson helps to improve the quality of knowledge, as it allows using the following types of communicative activities: listening, speaking, reading and writing (when performing exercises).

The use of video is justified psychologically: it is through the organs of vision and hearing that a person receives the bulk of information about the surrounding world [2, p. 12]. In addition, the use of video in the classroom increases the motivation and activity of students, creates certain conditions for independent work of students. The use of video contributes to the development of various aspects of students' mental activity, and above all, attention and memory. The video, thanks to the change of vivid impressions, allows students to concentrate their attention throughout the lesson. At the same time, attention is not contemplative, but mobilizing, since what is happening on the screen requires a response. Students are clearly convinced that language can be used as a means of communication [1]. The video method belongs to the group of visual methods.

When using the visual method, a number of conditions must be observed: - the video material used must correspond to the level of students' knowledge; - visibility should be used in moderation and it should be shown gradually and only at the appropriate moment of the lesson; - video viewing should be organized in such a way that all students can clearly see the material being demonstrated; - it is necessary to clearly highlight the main, essential issues; - think over in detail the explanations given during the demonstration of the video material; - the demonstrated video material should be precisely coordinated with the studied educational material, correspond to the studied topic.

Audio visualized information can be selected in accordance with the section under study from scientific and popular science films, feature films, from TV shows and other sources that are now available on the Internet. Here, for example, cartoons for younger schoolchildren can be used, and films for older students [3].

The audiovisual method completely excludes the use of the native language, especially at the initial stage of learning, since during this period interference complicates the formation of oral communication skills.

Modern technologies greatly simplify the use of the audiovisual method of teaching communicative skills in foreign language classes. It is possible to watch not only specialized educational films, but also game films that arouse more interest among students, thereby being an additional motivation for learning a foreign language.

Films are a valuable learning tool, because while watching the film, students get an idea of how the language they are learning is used in real life, a dynamic visual series shows the relationship between linguistic and paralinguistic aspects of the behavior of native speakers in situations of natural communication. In addition, the film performs a cognitive function - it introduces students to the country of the language being studied, its history, culture, and way of life [4].

Work with audio-visual material consists of several stages: preparatory - work with new language material, training in probabilistic forecasting, development of short-term and verbal-logical memory, directly viewing the material and checking the level of understanding of information along with the consolidation of new skills and abilities.

Pedagogical experience shows that the use of fiction films in the educational process deserves special consideration, since they have many didactic possibilities and can set the necessary context of activity. So, their use in English lessons allows:

- 1) Creating a variety of speech situations in teaching speaking;
- 2) increasing the enthusiasm and interest of students, diversify activities during the lesson;
- 3) simulating the language environment by unobtrusively introducing country-specific facts and phenomena;
- 4) conflict-free to compare the culture and features of life of the native country and the country of the studied language;
- 5) giving the content of the educational process a creative, problematic, research character;
- 6) paying attention to the intonation of the speakers and reveal their body language, such as facial expressions and gestures, which may have their own cultural characteristics;
- 7) increasing the effectiveness of the educational process, in particular, the communicative component, through the emotional sphere of students;
- 8) speeding up the process of acquiring new knowledge [5].

Let's consider the steps of working with a film.

At the preparatory stage, it is suggested to give students a brief historical background for a more complete and correct understanding of the events described in the film. In order to interest them in the topic and improve their oral and written speech skills, students can be invited to find information on their own, prepare projects on this topic, discuss them, organize debates.

Subsequently, upon completion of work with thematic fragments, it is worth showing the film in full, so that students have the opportunity not only to immerse themselves in the proposed language environment, but also to get a relatively complete idea of the film.

At this stage, the following types of exercises are offered:

1. translate with a dictionary and discuss options for translating new words (the list of words is compiled by the teacher on the basis of audio-visual material);
2. write out from the suggested options the words that you expect to hear in the thematic fragment, and the words that are not there;
3. choose the terms corresponding to the proposed definitions;
4. listen to a number of adjectives /verbs, name the nouns that are used with them;
5. name the meanings of words formed from known elements (for example, grateful, thankless);
6. listen to a number of speech formulas and name situations in a foreign language in which they can be used;
7. listen to and repeat phrases whose length exceeds the volume of short-term memory (10 or more words);
8. listen to the phrase, add to it a few more related in meaning;
9. listen to phrases containing realities, phraseological units, abbreviations, assume their probable translation;

10. suggest the subject of the proposed fragment on the basis of the elaborated material, highlight keywords, suggest options for the development of the situation.

This list of exercises is not exhaustive, but gives an idea of a possible variant of the preparatory stage of working with audiovisual material.

At the stage of viewing fragments of the film, in our opinion, it is impractical to perform any exercises, since in this case students need to focus on understanding and perceiving the information received, monitor the articulation and speech of the characters. After completing the work on the fragments, students are invited to watch the film in full, in this case, teacher can suggest marking unfamiliar or incomprehensible words and expressions for their subsequent discussion, or, if the level of language training of students allows, suggest writing out words related to a certain topic.

At the stage of checking the level of understanding of information, along with the consolidation of new skills and abilities, it is possible to use the following exercises:

1. mark true - false statement;
2. read the summary and insert the missing words corresponding to the meaning of the watched material;
3. get acquainted with two or three titles to the fragment, choose the most appropriate one, comment on the choice;
4. highlight the parts in the fragment, title them;
5. stage the fragment;
6. retell the dialogue/monologue from the fragment in the form of a monologue/dialogue;
7. evaluate the viewed fragment in terms of its novelty, informativeness;
8. discuss the problematic issues raised in the fragment;
9. answer the questions to the fragment;
10. choose from several possible answers the only correct one.

After completing the work with the fragments, students are offered a demonstration of the entire audiovisual material. Watching the film ends with exercises that allow the teacher to judge the level of complete and critical understanding of the audiovisual material:

1. answer questions about the general content and individual details;
2. make a summary / abstract/ review;
3. highlight the parts of the film and title them;
4. evaluate the actions of the actors;
5. organize a discussion based on various opinions about the material.

It is worth noting that the use of audiovisual material along with audio texts will diversify the learning process of foreign language and will contribute to the development of communicative skills. The use of fiction films in teaching is an additional motivation for learning a foreign language and contributes to foreign language acquisition.

Summarizing the above, the use of audiovisual technologies, namely fiction films, for teaching a foreign language, can be effective. Of course, the film only gives a pedagogical effect when it is used methodically competently and reasonably. To do this, it is necessary to choose a suitable fiction film that will correspond to the level of knowledge of a foreign language, the interests of students, their age, culture and will be gender identical. In addition, it is necessary to choose a video with a high degree of visual support, a clear image and sound, as well as with a clear accent. The uniqueness of films lies in the fact that they serve as an illustration to the presentation of educational material and naturally create a speech situation that encourages students to engage in conversation, express personal attitudes to events, as well as actively participate in the discussion of the film, which certainly contributes to the implementation of situational learning techniques. Working with videos introduces students to the accepted norms of speech interaction and the peculiarities of the communicative behavior of native speakers of the studied language. In addition, students are clearly convinced that a foreign language can be used as a means of communication, which is a source of motivation. And finally, movies broaden the horizons, i.e. students can learn a lot about the country

of the language being studied, about its culture and inhabitants, which facilitates communication with native speakers, makes it effective and successful.

REFERENCES

1. Asadullina, L.I., Duseev I.R. Teaching speaking through feature films // *Molodoj uchenyj*. – 2015. – № 11 (91). – P. 1244-1247.
2. Barmenkova, O. I. Videozanjatija v sisteme obuchenija inostranoj rechi [Videolessons in the system of teaching foreign language speech] // *Inostrannye jazyki v shkole*. – 1999. – №3. – P. 20-25.
3. Bidzhiev D.U., Petrova N.P. Audiovizual'nye sredstva kak jeffektivnyj istochnik povyshenija kachestva obuchenija [Audiovisual means as an effective source of improving the quality of education] // *Obrazovanie. Nauka. Innovacii: juzhnoe izmerenie*. – 2015. – №4 (42). – P. 129-137
4. Verisokin, Ju.I. Videofil'my kak sredstvo motivacii shkol'nikov pri obuchenii inostrannym jazykam [Videos as a means of motivating schoolchildren when teaching foreign languages] // *Inostrannye jazyki v shkole*. – 2003. – №5. – P. 31-35.
5. Passov, E.I. Osnovy kommunikativnoj teorii i tehnologii inojazychnogo obrazovanija: metodicheskoe posobie dlja prepodavatelej russkogo jazyka kak inostrannogo [Fundamentals of communicative theory and technology of foreign language education: a methodological guide for teachers of Russian as a foreign language]. – M.: Russkij jazyk. Kursy, 2010. – 568 p.